

EXECUTIVE COACHING FOR LEADERSHIP IN ORGANIZATIONS AND ITS BENEFITS FOR MANAGERIAL PERFORMANCE-A CONCEPTUAL STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Executive coaching is a formal engagement in which a qualified coach, works with an organizational leader in a series of dynamic and confidential sessions designed to establish and achieve clear goals that will result in improved managerial performance. Coaching is fundamentally a process for facilitating learning and change, which is another way to describe development (Kram & Ting, 2006). Why do executives need coaching? Can't they do it on their own? It is because no individual in this world is accurate in making his own assessment. Moreover, it takes lot of time and effort to research and understand one's own strengths and limitations. Why struggle seeking answers on your own through trial and error when help is at your fingertips? A professional coach can help improve your life, career and work performance.

A lot of managerial professionals are seeking executive coaching in order to enhance their leadership skills, expand their advancement opportunities or ascertain whether they should be moving on. As it is often lonely at the top, many executives feel restrained and isolated and are rightly concerned about sharing their issues in-house for fear they will not remain private. They may be tired of the pressure, the numbers game, the manoeuvres or the public relations facade. They may have been subtly told their management or leadership skills need improving. Or, they are looking to forge new opportunities for themselves. There is no doubt that for these individuals the stakes are high. At the same time, there is an increasing need to stop thinking about their concerns and start doing something. People come to executive coaching basically to address two major challenges namely, the problems they face in day-to-day work which we call as remedial and secondly those who are already good, & want to become the best, which is called generative or growth-focused. Executive coaching helps managers in rediscovering and reconnecting to one's purpose in life and work, examining regularly the assumptions and behavior in the light of one's aspirations and goals, developing and practicing new behaviours and skills, expanding one's sphere of possibilities, transforming one's own context by creating a new leadership identity and committing to take effective action.

Keywords : Executive training, Training & development, Coaching, Employee training, Performance

INTRODUCTION

Executive coaching is a formal engagement in which a qualified coach, works with an organizational leader in a series of dynamic and confidential sessions designed to establish and achieve clear goals that will result in improved managerial performance (CCL, 2003). As of now, executive coaching is availed of by managerial level people in business organizations and such services are generally provided by external consultants who are specialized in the areas of personal growth and interpersonal effectiveness. The fees for coaching is either paid by the organization or borne by the manager from his personal sources.

While the term coaching in the traditional sense refers to work related technical advice to resolve on the job hurdles for enhanced performance, executive coaching never deals with technical problems; rather it is a behavioral intervention. In executive coaching, the manager and the coach work together to assess and understand the former's job role and his developmental need, challenge current constraints, explore new possibilities, ensure accountability and support for reaching the identified goals and sustaining development.

Executive coaching is above all, a way of learning. It aims at transformation, driven by the client's own choices. Based on the professional relationship of mutual trust and respect, it focuses on the client's aspirations and goals and works towards developing commitment and action in pursuing them. It takes the form of systematic and purposeful conversations between the client and coach over a few months, as per the framework agreed to at the outset.

Since the advent of appraisal interviews and other forms of feedback, most people have a fairly good idea of their strengths and weakness at work. However, knowing what you want to change and how to go about changing it require two different approaches. Executive Coaching involves one to one meetings with a specialist trained in how people change and the manager who seeks change for himself. It is designed to pinpoint specific changes that will make managers improve performance and lead a better life.

PRINCIPLES

Executive coaching is a relatively new approach to management development. In this connection Ting and Hart (2004) have suggested six principles for executive coaches as under:

1. *Create a safe but challenging environment.* It means encouraging the learners to stretch beyond their comfort zones, by creating a risk-free atmosphere.
2. *Work with coachee's agenda.* Understand what the learner wants rather than prescribing what you want the learner to be. Involve the learner at every stage of Coaching for deciding the further course of action.
3. *Facilitate implementation.* Support performance by providing the needed resources and encouragement.
4. *Advocate self-awareness.* Encourage the learner to know the meaning and impact of his present behaviours and what it takes to achieve excellence at work and in life.
5. *Promote sustainable learning from experience.* Educate and motivate the learner to learn from the mistakes, failures and successes that occur at work.
6. *Model what you coach.* As a coach, practice what you coach. If coaches cannot practice what they preach, then learners cannot have faith in the words of the coaches. Moreover, learners must also have a role model to imitate the success behaviours.

LEVELS OF COACHING

Coaching is fundamentally a process for facilitating learning and change, which is another way to describe development (Kram & Ting, 2006). Executive coaching may occur at multiple levels namely a) behavioural, b) underlying drivers and c) root causes. Behavioural level involves observable action both verbal and non-verbal. Underlying drivers include personal styles, preferences, orientations, aspirations, motivations, mental models, assumptions, values, core needs and life experiences. Root causes include life experiences, trauma, psychological disorders and unmanageable personal problems.

THE TARGET GROUP

Executive coaching is not for the mentally sick people. A coach is not a therapist. Rather, he is like a peer working with admirable people who are often highly advanced in their understanding of themselves. They are certainly not sick. Instead, they are exceptional people eagerly striving to develop themselves. The essence of executive coaching is in helping the client move up from 'already good'. The people who come to executive coaching are highly functional, often star performers, yet they have room for growth. Growth often begins from dissatisfaction with what is already achieved.

People come to executive coaching basically to address two major challenges namely, the problems they face in day-to-day work which we call as remedial and secondly those who are already good, & want to become the best, which is called generative or growth-focused, Remedial change is needed when manager has a problem.

He may say things like "I lack the confidence to present to large groups of people", or "I'm overworked and I can't seem to delegate," or "I have a personality clash with my boss".

Managers looking for generative change may say "I'm a pretty good manager and I really like to improve my ability to support my people during this corporate change," or "I've just got promoted to the Board and I realize the need for new ways to influence my fellow directors." This is generative change - taking strength and making it even better or broadening a skill so it is effective in even more situations.

PURPOSE AND SIGNIFICANCE

Why do executives need coaching? Can't they do it on their own? It is because no individual in this world is accurate in making his own assessment. Moreover, it takes a lot of time and effort to research and understand one's own strengths and limitations. Why struggle seeking answers on your own through trial and error when help is at your fingertips? A professional coach can help improve your life, career and work performance.

A lot of managerial professionals are seeking executive coaching in order to enhance their leadership skills, expand their advancement opportunities or ascertain whether they should be moving on. As it is often lonely at the top, many executives feel restrained and isolated and are rightly concerned about sharing their issues in-house for fear they will not remain private. They may be tired of the pressure, the numbers game, the manoeuvres or the public relations facade. They may have been subtly told their management or leadership skills need improving. Or, they are looking to forge new opportunities for themselves. There is no doubt that for these individuals the stakes are high. At the same time, there is an increasing need to stop thinking about their concerns and start doing something.

For those bold enough to lead in this age of uncertainty the challenges are immense. Our world is a new world and it requires a new kind of leadership. Executive coaching can create resonant leaders. Resonant leaders are in tune with those around them. These results in people wring in sync with each other in tune with each other's thoughts and emotions. Leaders who can create resonance are people who either intuitively understand or have worked hard to develop emotional intelligence (Boyatzis R. & McKee A, 2005).

Don't be under the impression that leaders and the educated are always in the learning frontline. According to Argyris (1993), surprisingly, it is often the most educated, successful and motivated individuals who find it the most difficult to learn, using their analytical skills as a defence against acknowledging or learning from their mistakes. Real learning is possible only when professionals begin to identify the gaps between their intended and actual behaviour. By the time the executives reach the top levels of their organizations, they may appear to some as feedback-proof and unwilling to change. Even if they feel something is missing in their leadership, they are often unable to get others to confirm or talk openly about that possibility (Grubb and Ting, 2006).

It is likely that as a business leader you have no peers to consult with or seek advice from. Subordinates think that you have all the answers and need no help. You may also think the same way. You may feel that you have many things to do and not enough time to address them. You may often engage in tunnel vision, being so focused on one aspect of the business that others are neglected. You may have unresolved personal and emotional issues, such as low self-confidence or a marriage in jeopardy, which interferes with your work performance.

Executive coaching is not a luxury to exhaust the budget allocated for HRD function. Rather, it is a necessity to equip managers for succeeding in the changed business environment. In this context, it is noteworthy to have a brief look at the changed environment of doing business. In the past, the managers were working in bureaucratic organizations with adequate powers to get the work done from the subordinates by issuing formal orders. Now, organizations have shed their bureaucratic hierarchies and subordinates have been empowered to work in their own ways. As a result, the business managers in leadership roles have to learn, influencing people on whom they have no control, to get the work done.

Executive coaching has to be strategic and individualized. A balance has to be struck between the organization and the individuals. In order to engage and to motivate, coaching must be individually tailored to the needs and aspirations of each particular individual. To deliver business results, the approach must also be organizationally tailored to the strategy, vision and values of the organization (Freas, 2000).

PROCESS OF EXECUTIVE COACHING

Executive coaching cannot be conducted in a disorganized way. Sequential steps are necessary to get the desired results. Thus, it uses a seven-step process to accomplish its developmental objectives. Successful coaches have various models to provide structure and purpose to the conversations. Invariably they, explore questions about personal purpose or mission, strength and gifts, the organizational context, assumptions about leadership, keys to professional development, and new ways of thinking and behaving. In the coaching sessions, the two people (ie coach and manager) focus on the employee's aspirations, attitudes and behavior in the specific context of his or her organizational responsibilities. The client's commitment to professional growth and openness to being coached are crucial to success, as is the coach's ability to be fully present; listening, supporting, probing, challenging and offering different perspectives and options; in an atmosphere of complete confidentiality.

Most of the HRD programs involve monetary and people resources for implementation. It is therefore necessary to assess and identify the need for executive coaching. The issues to be considered for assessing the need here are

- * Is this employee working in leadership role?
- * Has he a developmental need which can be addressed through executive coaching?
- * Is he interested in developing himself through executive coaching?
- To check important leadership dimensions like
 - * Understanding other's perspective
 - * Involving everyone in decision-making
 - * Communication and feedback
 - * Openness
 - * Influencing others
 - * Empowering the subordinates
 - * Trusting others
 - * Conscientiousness

Fig 1: Analysis of coaching needs for executives

Seven steps in the process of executive coaching are

- 1) Identify the need
- 2) Decide to address by executive coaching
- 3) Identify the right coach
- 4) Preliminary meeting
- 5) Identify developmental areas
- 6) Identify and undergo the interventions
- 7) Review, evaluate and terminate – Growth

CONCLUSION

The focus of executive coaching is to help people in managerial roles to understand their own strengths and limitations, to practice the behaviours needed for success in their work lives and finally, for attaining their managerial goals. Executive coaching will be beneficial for managers in leadership roles (like those who have to get the work done through others) than those who work on their own research or back-office work by sitting in the corner work station. Executive coaching is designed and delivered on an individual basis by customizing to the needs of concerned managers.

Executive coaching helps managers in rediscovering and reconnecting to one's purpose in life and work, examining regularly the assumptions and behaviour in the light of one's aspirations and goals, developing and practicing new behaviours and skills, expanding one's sphere of possibilities, transforming one's own context by creating a new leadership identity and committing to take effective action.

A coach is not an authority figure in executive coaching. Above all, the relationship between an executive and a coach is a collaborative one. Together, the manager and the coach will assess the circumstances, strengths, weaknesses, and developmental opportunities. The manager will work with the coach to create developmental action plans. Once the manager executes the agreed plans, he along with the coach, will jointly review the results and define new action plans towards further growth. Throughout this process, the level of benefits the manager receives from using a coach is directly related to the former's willingness and ability to take an active role in every aspect of the coaching engagement. A good coach will help the manager develop clarity of purpose and focus on action. Executive coaching engagements usually last from 6 to 18 months.

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